

Earlier, fatty acid compositions of *S. grandiflora*⁵ and *S. aegyptica*⁶ were determined by fractionation methods. It is found that the present observations are different from the previous one.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to ICAR-USDA for providing financial assistance

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Fatty Acid Composition and Characteristics of *Cassia glauca* Seed Oil

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Manuscript received 23 May 1990, accepted 26 July 1990

CASSIA glauca (N.O. Leguminosae) plant occur throughout India. No work has been reported so far on fixed oil from its seeds. Phytochemical screening of forest seed oils is a subject of intensive research to explore new alternative sources for conventional oils. It was therefore considered worthwhile to isolate the fixed oil from the seeds of *C. glauca* (collected locally) using glc technique.

Experimental

Cleaned and dried seeds (2 kg) were crushed and extracted exhaustively with light petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). Removal of the solvent yielded a yellowish oil with a faint odour, which was purified through animal charcoal and Fuller's earth. The oil was subjected to various qualitative tests, e.g. picric acid test¹ for epoxy group and Halphen test² for cyclopropene moiety. The characteristics of the purified oil determined according to standard AOCS³ methods are given in the Table 1. The mixed fatty acids were converted to their methyl esters⁴. Glc of the methyl esters was carried out on a CIC gas chromatograph equipped with flame ionisation detector using stainless steel column (3 mm x 2 m) packed with 20% DEGS on chromosorb and using

nitrogen as carrier gas. The injection port, columns and flame ionisation detector block were maintained at 260, 190 and 190° respectively. The methyl esters were identified⁵ by co-glc with authentic samples.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF THE OIL

Yield of oil (%)	5
Specific gravity (at 30°)	0.916
Refractive index (at 40°)	1.468
Moisture content (%)	3.9
Acid value	1.8
Saponification value	192
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	4.12
Iodine value (Wijs method)	96.2
Fatty acids (%)	
Palmitic	30.354 3
Stearic	1.317 6
Oleic	23.497 9
Linoleic	42.916 9
Linolenic	1.627 1
Arachidic	0.286 2

Results and Discussion

The results gave no indication of conjugation or *trans*-unsaturation or any other functional groups in the oil. No epoxy function could be detected in it. The oil is of non-drying type and indicates its potential for edible use after due processing. However, the seeds cannot be a good source of oil to be exploited economically.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. J. P. Pathak of H.B.T.I., Kanpur, for glc facilities.

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Synthesis of new 3-Substituted-*s*-triazolo-[3,4-*b*]-8-methylpyrazolo[3',4'-*e*](5*H*)-[1,3,4]thiadiazines

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Manuscript received 15 January 1990, revised 15 May 1990, accepted 3 July 1990

IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new *s*-triazolothiadiazines as potential anthelmintic agents^{1,2,3}, the hitherto unreported title compounds (3) have been prepared by the condensation of the corresponding 3-substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl no	R	M p °C	Yield %	Mol formula	ν_{\max} cm^{-1}
1	CH ₃	197d	76	C ₇ H ₈ N ₆ S	3 240, 3 110 (NH), 1 600 (C=N)
2	C ₂ H ₅	192	82	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₆ S	3 240, 3 140, 1 610
3	C ₆ H ₅	218	84	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₆ S	3 362, 1 610
4	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	152d	77	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ S	3 420, 1 620
5	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	202	76	C ₁₂ H ₉ ClN ₆ S	3 300, 1 610
6	4'-Pyridyl	232	77	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₇ S	3 280, 1 630
7	C ₆ H ₅ -O-CH ₂	188	81	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₆ OS	3 310, 1 610, 1 230, 1 025 (Ar-O-R)
8	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	220	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ OS	3 310, 1 590, 1 220, 1 202, 1 030
9	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-CH ₂	230	78	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ ClN ₆ OS	3 310, 1 605, 1 228, 1 020

*C, H, N and S analyses were found to be satisfactory for all compounds

4-triazoles¹ (1) with 4-bromo-3-methyl-pyrazol-5-one (2) following the reported procedure. The structures of the products were based on elemental analyses and ir spectral data (Table 1).

The ir spectra (KBr) of 3 did not show bands due to carbonyl and mercapto groups, thus confirming the cyclic structure 3. Strong intensity absorption bands at 1 070–1 000 cm^{-1} due to aromatic ether linkage (Ph-O-R) at position-3 were observed for 3 (R=aryloxymethyl), and NH vibrations were observed at 3 600–3 200 cm^{-1} .

Acknowledgements

Sincere thanks are due to Prof. V. S. Darshane, Head of the Department of Chemistry and Dr. S. A. Suryawanshi, Director-in-charge, The Institute of Science, Bombay for facilities.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Tetra-bromo-1,4-benzoquinone using Diheteroalicyclic Compounds as Reagents

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Manuscript received 20 November 1989, revised 24 April 1990, accepted 9 July 1990

BROMOSUBSTITUTED 1,4-benzoquinones are reported to be stronger acids as compared to chloro-substituted quinones¹. 2,3,5,6-Tetrabromo-1,4-benzoquinone (bromanil) is an oxidant² and used as an analytical reagent³. Some coulometric titrations^{4,5} and spectrophotometric methods^{6,7} are suggested for chloranil. However, no attempt has, so far been made for the determination of bromanil, except the one method reported by us earlier⁶.

Bromanil is a good π -acceptor and it is known to form electron donor-acceptor complexes with heteroalicyclic compounds⁸. Based on this, three diheteroalicyclic compounds, morpholine, thiomorpholine and piperazine were examined as reagents for the determination of bromanil by spectrophotometric method. We present here the results of such study.

Experimental

Bromanil was prepared and purified as reported earlier⁸. Morpholine and thiomorpholine (both Fluka) were purified by distillation on potassium hydroxide, while piperazine (EGA) was recrystallised from cyclohexane.

A Carl-Zeiss Spekol spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorbance.

Stock solutions of bromanil (5×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3}) and the reagents (each about 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) were prepared in chloroform. An aliquot (0.3–1.5 ml) of

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